

YOUTH SPIRITUALITY AND NATIONAL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19060348>

Annotation: In this article, the basis of national education is the study of the upbringing of young people, the factors that claim to be their spiritual needs, and this problem continues to manifest itself as one of the most important issues in the policy that is currently being conducted in our society.

Basic words: spirituality, youth, upbringing, heritage, value, history, national idea, democracy.

Introduction. If society is the universal form of life, the family is its fundamental unit. The family develops in accordance with general, special, and social laws. At the same time, it is a relatively independent social institution that not only reflects all of society's contradictions but also possesses its own internal conflicts and natural sources of development. The changes that occur in society and the family are interconnected. Today's political, economic, spiritual, and psychological transformations have created the necessary opportunities for young people to form a positive attitude towards family and family relations. Therefore, the family not only serves the function of population growth but is also a conducive environment for an individual's self-expression, the acquisition of socially significant qualities and traits, and the formation of social culture.

Moral upbringing in the family, at school, in the workplace, and in the mahalla, combined with the power of public opinion, the influence of mass media, and the authority of the clergy - all of these must be directed toward forming a steadfast resistance in our people to any action that involves breaking the law.

The declaration of 1998 as the "Year of the Family" in our republic engaged all state and non-governmental organizations in solving the socio-economic problems of the family. In February 1998, by a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republican Scientific and Practical Center "Oila" was established.

Literature review: Scientists have conducted a number of studies on the study of the significance of values in national upbringing and the spiritual development of youth. In particular, D.O.Ortikova, I.R.Khodzhamurodov, I.E.Khudoyberdiyev, M.Mamatov, G.S.Karamatov, F.A.Primova, Z.E.Markayev, T.K.Komilova, M.T.Tadzhibaev, N.M.Musaeva, A.A.Kambarov, Y.M.Yakubov, M.A.Karimova, and others.

Research methodology: In the current process of forming a legal, democratic, and civil society in our country, it is crucial to scientifically analyze the role of national upbringing and youth spirituality. The analysis of state policy on restoring the spiritual and cultural heritage of our ancestors, particularly national values, after Uzbekistan gained independence, is of great importance. This includes examining the specific approaches to national values in the restoration of ancestral heritage; the influence of national values on the formation of youth spirituality; methods for elevating the spiritual culture of youth, and the role of national and

Islamic values. Furthermore, scientifically substantiating - based on the principles of succession, historicity, and logic - the importance of national upbringing and the family as key factors in combating spiritual threats is a pressing issue.

Analysis and results: The family is the starting point in the legal education of young people and the education system. The family environment, the relationship between children and parents, the formed system of upbringing serve as an important factor in the formation of children's initial views on law.

If the atmosphere in the family is built on mutual respect, nobility, and honesty, and if the heads of the family sincerely fulfill their duties, good citizens will emerge from such a unit of society. Abu Ali ibn Sina said that "bad upbringing in the family can have a negative impact not only on the family itself, but also on other families around it"[1].

Education and upbringing have always been the most important urgent task facing humanity that needs to be solved. It is also organized on the basis of people's experience, achievements, customs, and traditions. That is, we have many established customs and eternal traditions related to education and upbringing. Even today, it is advisable to widely use them in the upbringing of young people. We must always remember that the future of our country depends on how our young generation is raised, what spiritual qualities they possess, how actively our children approach life, and what noble goals they serve[2].

The growing volume of knowledge and information will undoubtedly stimulate the expansion of people's worldview and the elevation of their spirituality. At the same time, it is becoming a crucial task to develop the ability to distinguish truthful, objective, and useful information from the incessant and unsystematic flow of messages.

The reforms being implemented in our republic's education and upbringing system are aimed precisely at this goal. Indeed, from an ideological perspective, this issue is fully consistent with the principles of the "National Program for Personnel Training" and the Law "On Education." In general, according to the national model of education and upbringing, renewing the education system naturally creates the necessity to study our national heritage and integrate it into pedagogical thought.

The ideological foundation of our national heritage has always been the upbringing of the individual and the study of factors that cater to their spiritual needs. This issue continues to manifest as one of the most important priorities in the policies of our society today.

The educational process is shaped by many factors, including the convergence of different countries around the world, which are truly global and decisive for the fate of human civilization. Among these factors, the emerging commonalities and national specificities are of particular importance.

The unique potential of education today is linked not only to equipping the human mind with new, rapid capabilities but also with restructuring its consciousness. A new stage in the development of human civilization is changing perceptions of the human formation process, personal qualities, life goals, and values. The education system places qualitatively new demands on the rising generation.

The improvement of the education and upbringing system, in turn, largely depends on the consistent introduction of new, modern, and advanced pedagogical technologies in this field. Considering that the effectiveness of education is determined by the student's level of active

participation in the process, new teaching methods and forms create opportunities for learners to think independently and approach their studies creatively.

There is a logical connection with the aforementioned issues in the fact that the main objective of the national model for personnel training is to form a well-rounded individual and a highly qualified specialist. Indeed, the national model for personnel training consists not only of education and upbringing, but also encompasses many interconnected stages of life. Our national model reflects the organic unity and cooperation of the individual, society, and the state, as well as continuous education, science, and production, and their interconnectedness.

The individual is the main subject and object of the personnel training system, the consumer of services in the field of education, and their implementer [3]. This is why our ancestors, in matters of education and upbringing, acted with consideration for the individual's personality and their characteristics. As our great thinker Abu Nasr al-Farabi wrote, before beginning the work of education and upbringing, it is necessary to study the personal traits of the learners [4].

It should be particularly emphasized that the content of the concept of the national model of education and upbringing is linked to the national way of life and spiritual and moral traditions. For this reason, when analyzing the main features of the national model within the education system, the sociologists and philosophers of our republic strive to reveal its role and significance in national upbringing.

In particular, according to the renowned philosopher, academician E.Y. Yusupov, these features of national upbringing will yield a positive effect only if they are linked with our national traditions and values, in addition to being able to harmonize with the modern education system [5].

It is well-known that the primary goal of the national model of education and upbringing is to cultivate a well-rounded individual. On this issue, the scientists of our republic have also put forward their own specific concepts [6]. A spiritually mature person acts on the basis of reason and intellect. Loyalty to one's homeland, people, and nation is also considered a sign of being cultured, spiritual, well-rounded, and morally pure. Only when the greatest virtues, such as honesty and modesty, are combined can one become a truly well-rounded person [7].

Being a highly qualified specialist - whether a scientist, architect, artist, or military officer - does not in itself signify complete personal development. To achieve this, a person must pass through the necessary school of life and embark on a path of faith and conviction [8]. In fostering this completeness, it is advisable to publish and promote literature related to our own Eastern cultural and spiritual traditions, their uniqueness, and their merits.

A unique feature of the mahalla, where a person's entire life unfolds, is that every family and individual living within it is shaped before the eyes of the community. The upbringing of the youth is a process inextricably linked to the activities of the mahalla. As the closest level of governance to the people, the mahalla should be a major center of upbringing, spirituality, and enlightenment for young people.

The roles of the family, the mahalla, the mass media, and state and non-governmental public organizations are invaluable in enhancing the moral culture of the youth. Therefore, it is undeniable that young people, nurtured in the spirit of the national idea, will form the foundation of our bright present and future.

In today's world of intensifying ideological struggles, it is crucial to instill in the hearts of our youth a healthy respect for our Motherland, our rich history, our national values, our native language - the immortal spirit of our nation - and the sacred religion inherited from our ancestors. It is also vital that we form their ideological immunity.

The national idea plays a significant role in elevating the spirituality of our youth and in their upbringing in the national spirit. Today, for our country, which is confidently advancing on the path to building a new life and joining the ranks of developed nations, the issue of a national idea is of paramount importance. As long as the national idea is founded on goodness, the need to organize targeted advocacy efforts in the fight against destructive ideologies will only become more urgent.

The school plays a special role in the fight against ideological attacks based on the national idea. Therefore, it is no coincidence that large-scale reforms are being carried out in our country today in the field of education and upbringing. Based on the idea "From National Revival to National Ascent," Uzbekistan has entered a new era of development, and reforms in the socio-economic and spiritual-educational spheres are becoming a great national goal, a nationwide movement.

As our enlightened Jadid ancestors said, "Salvation is in education, salvation is in upbringing, salvation is in knowledge. Because all noble goals are achieved through knowledge and upbringing." After all, the cornerstone of the development of any state is directly related to the attention paid to education.

Conclusions and suggestions: In conclusion, historically, special attention has been paid to the education and upbringing of children as a very delicate and serious issue. This laid the foundation for the future economic, political, social, cultural, and spiritual development of the country. The President of our country, quoting the wise words of Eastern sages: "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is good upbringing, the greatest poverty is ignorance!" was absolutely right when he emphasized that mastering modern knowledge, possessing genuine enlightenment and high culture is becoming a constant life necessity, that to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also all members of our society, first of all, knowledge, enlightenment, and high spirituality are necessary, and where there is no knowledge, there are cases of backwardness, ignorance, and, of course, deviation from the right path.

In the fight against ideological attacks, the national idea of our country gives each of us confidence in the future, strength, energy, and courage, and mobilizes our youth, our people, and our nation for great and constructive deeds, for uniting in the defense of the Motherland, the nation, and independence.

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